

COMBINATION OF DESIGN OF EXPERIMENTS AND SIMPLE ADDITIVE WEIGHTING METHODS: A NEW METHOD FOR RAPID MULTI-CRITERIA DECISION MAKING

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Abstract

Multi-criteria decision making to choose the best option is a complicated task but a required activity in all fields. The problem will be more complicated if, after making a decision, one/several options are added to the list of options to be ranked. In this case, if only a certain multi-criteria decision making method is used, the decision-making shall be required to be started over again. This study recommends a simple solution to overcome this situation. The recommended solution is a combination between the Design Of Experiments method and a certain multi-criteria decision making method. Simple Additive Weighting method was selected in this study as one of the multi-criteria decision making methods for testing. Use the Design Of Experiments method to design an experiment matrix with the main input parameters being the criteria of options. The Simple Additive Weighting method is applied to calculate the output value of each experiment, called the score of the experiment. Develop a mathematical relation between the scores of the experiments and the criteria. This relation is used to recalculate the scores for options to be ranked. Three different cases were performed to evaluate the effectiveness of the new method. The results of ranking alternatives by new method have been compared with when using other methods. Sensitivity analysis was also performed in each case. The generation of different scenarios is done using different methods to determine the weights for the criteria. The best alternative determined when using the new method is always similar to when using other methods. In addition, when using the new method, the best alternative is determined regardless of the method of determining the weights for the criteria. The obtained results have proved the accuracy of the methodology and the advantages of the recommended method. Future work is also mentioned in the last part of this article.

Keywords: MCDM, DOE method, SAW method, DOESAW method, Rapid decision making.

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1. Introduction

Choosing an option that is considered to be the best among the others is a necessity taking place in all different fields. If each option is described by many criteria, such task is often very complicated. Then the selection of the best option is required to simultaneously take account of the criteria, and called Multi-Criteria Decision Making (MCDM). Currently, there are hundreds of different MCDM methods recommended by scientists to perform this task [1].

Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) is the oldest of the MCDM methods. It is also considered to be the most commonly used method thanks to its simplicity [2–6]. The advantage of this method is performing a proportional linear transformation of the unprocessed data, which means that the order of relative magnitude of the benchmarks remains the same [7, 8]. For that very reason, despite being the oldest, this method or its modified variables is still widely used in recently published studies: to evaluate flood control projects [9]; to choose air conditioners [10]; to choose schools [11, 12]; to evaluate national football teams participating in the 2018 World Cup [13]; to choose employees to be recruited into the company [2]; to choose students who are entitled to grants [14]; to serve the recruitment for lecturers of a University [15]; to rank secondary school teachers [16]; to rank singers in a band [17]; to evaluate the sustainability of real estate projects [18]; to choose industrial robots, Flexible Manufacturing Systems and non-traditional machining methods [19], and so on. Thus, it can be seen that the SAW method has been successfully applied to make multi-criteria decisions in many different fields. However, SAW, like all other MCDM methods, has one thing in common that is if, after the ranking of options has ended, one/several options are added to the

list, such ranking is required to be started over again. This is seen as a common limitation of all existing MCDM methods.

This study recommends a novel approach to overcome this situation. The method is recommended by combining the Design Of Experiments (DOE) method with the SAW method, referred to as the DOESAW method. Section 2 of this article presents the steps following the SAW method. Details of the steps to perform the ranking of options according to the DOESAW method are presented in section 3 of this article. Contents applying the DOESAW method to rank options in a number of different cases are included in section 4. The discussion on results obtained and conclusions drawn is the final content of this article.

2. Materials and methods

2. 1. SAW method

The steps to perform multi-criteria decision making by the SAW method are as follows [20, 21]:

Step 1: Develop the decision matrix as shown in **Table 1**.

Table 1

Decision-making Matrix

No.	C_1	C_2	C_j	C_n
A_1	x_{11}	x_{12}	x_{1j}	x_{1n}
A_2	x_{21}	x_{22}	x_{2j}	x_{2n}
A_i	x_{i1}	x_{i2}	x_{ij}	x_{in}
A_m	x_{m1}	x_{m2}	x_{mj}	x_{mn}

Of which: x_{ij} is the value of criterion C_j at option A_i , with $i = 1 \div m$, $j = 1 \div n$.

Step 2: Determine the normalized values according to the following two formulas:

– for criteria as large as possible:

$$n_{ij} = \frac{x_{ij}}{\max x_{ij}}; \quad (1)$$

– for criteria as small as possible:

$$n_{ij} = \frac{\min x_{ij}}{x_{ij}}. \quad (2)$$

Step 3: Calculate scores for each option according to formula (3):

$$S_i = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \cdot n_{ij}. \quad (3)$$

Of which w_j is the weight of criterion j .

Step 4: Rank the options according to the principle that the best solution is the one with the largest S_i .

2. 2. DOESAW method

The steps to carry out multi-criteria decision making according to the recommended method (DOESAW method) are as follows:

Step 1: Develop a decision-making matrix (similar to step 1 of the SAW method).

Step 2: Determine the maximum and minimum value of each criterion as shown in **Table 2**.

Step 3: Build an experimental matrix with the main input parameters which are the criteria.

Experimental matrix forms commonly used to build a relation between input parameters and output parameters include: Box-Behnken; Central Composite Design (CCD); two-level full (2^k), where k is the number of input parameters. Of the three forms just listed, the last one is the simplest that is often used and still ensures the required accuracy [22]. The design of an experimental matrix is very simple with the support from statistical software, such as Minitab. Assuming with

three input parameters (three criteria: C_1, C_2, C_3), the experimental matrix designed in the form of two-level full will include eight experiments as shown in **Table 3**.

Table 2

Minimum and maximum values of each criterion

No.	Min	Max
C_1	$\text{Min}(C_{i1}), i = 1 \div m$	$\text{Max}(C_{i1}), i = 1 \div m$
C_2	$\text{Min}(C_{i2}), i = 1 \div m$	$\text{Max}(C_{i2}), i = 1 \div m$
C_j	$\text{Min}(C_{ij}), i = 1 \div m$	$\text{Max}(C_{ij}), i = 1 \div m$
C_n	$\text{Min}(C_{in}), i = 1 \div m$	$\text{Max}(C_{in}), i = 1 \div m$

Table 3

Two-level full experimental matrix when the number of criteria is equal to three

Exp.	C_1	C_2	C_3
1	Min(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Max(C_3)
2	Max(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Min(C_3)
3	Min(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Min(C_3)
4	Max(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Min(C_3)
5	Max(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Max(C_3)
6	Min(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Max(C_3)
7	Max(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Max(C_3)
8	Min(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Min(C_3)

Step 4: Add a column to the left of the experimental matrix. This column contains the values of score S_i as it is calculated using the SAW method, as shown in **Table 4**.

Table 4

Additional column containing the score values of the experiments

Exp.	C_1	C_2	C_3	S_i
1	Min(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Max(C_3)	S_1
2	Max(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Min(C_3)	S_2
3	Min(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Min(C_3)	S_3
4	Max(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Min(C_3)	S_4
5	Max(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Max(C_3)	S_5
6	Min(C_1)	Max(C_2)	Max(C_3)	S_6
7	Max(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Max(C_3)	S_7
8	Min(C_1)	Min(C_2)	Min(C_3)	S_8

Step 5: Build an equation showing the relation between the score of experiments and the criteria as (4):

$$S = f(C_j), j = 1 \div n. \quad (4)$$

Step 6: Evaluate the accuracy of equation (4) through statistical factors.

Step 7: Use formula (4) to recalculate the scores for options to be ranked and conduct ranking them. In addition, it is possible to use equation (4) to calculate the score for options added to the list of options. This is an outstanding advantage of the recommended method.

Several examples are made in the next section of the study with the aim to evaluate the effectiveness of the DOESAW method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Multi-criteria decision making in the turning process

Data on nine options of a turning process were borrowed for use in this case (Table 5) [23]. Four criteria are applied to evaluate each option including cutting force in the x direction (C_1), cutting force in the y direction (C_2), cutting force in the z direction (C_3), and material removal yield (C_4). Of these four criteria, only C_4 is the criterion as large as possible, the rest is the criterion as small as possible. The task of multi-criteria decision making is to identify an option out of nine ones where it is simultaneously guaranteed that C_1 , C_2 , C_3 are considered minimum, and C_4 is considered maximum. Seven methods including *SAW*, Weighted Aggregates Sum Product Assessment (*WASPAS*), Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (*TOPSIS*), Vlsekriterijumska optimizacijal KOMPromisno Resenje (*VIKOR*), Multiobjective Optimization On the basis of Ratio Analysis (*MOORA*), Complex PRoportional Assessment (*COPRAS*), and Proximity Indexed Value (*PIV*) were also applied to accomplish this task [23]. When performing this task, the weight of criteria C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , C_4 were identified by the Entropy method, with values equal to 0.2427, 0.25976, 0.24616, and 0.25138, respectively. The ranking results of options when applying the above methods will be used to compare with the ranking results when applying the DOESAW method.

Table 5
Data of case 1 [23]

No.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4
A1	59.844	187.437	44.165	11.561
A2	87.943	199.762	99.125	49.062
A3	78.913	127.456	69.874	109.108
A4	54.816	172.714	60.19	28.588
A5	63.117	180.361	68.869	99.039
A6	68.79	113.951	70.694	61.669
A7	46.654	116.88	92.222	57.177
A8	44.989	162.337	63.25	55.462
A9	54.846	167.837	74.165	151.09

The multi-criteria decision making for data in Table 5 by the DOESAW method is performed in turn as follows.

Build a decision-making matrix which is Table 5.

Identify the minimum and maximum values of each criterion, with the results shown in Table 6.

Table 6
Minimum and maximum values of each criterion (case 1)

No.	Min	Max
C_1	44.989	87.943
C_2	113.951	199.762
C_3	44.165	99.125
C_4	11.561	151.09

Build a two-level full experimental matrix consisting of sixteen experiments as shown in Table 7.

Table 7
Experimental matrix and results (case 1)

Exp.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	S_i
1	87.943	113.951	44.165	151.09	0.88146
2	44.989	199.762	44.165	151.09	0.88842
3	87.943	113.951	99.125	11.561	0.51283
4	87.943	199.762	99.125	151.09	0.63339
5	44.989	199.762	99.125	11.561	0.51979
6	87.943	113.951	44.165	11.561	0.64931
7	44.989	113.951	99.125	151.09	0.86352
8	44.989	113.951	44.165	151.09	1.00000
9	44.989	113.951	99.125	11.561	0.63137
10	87.943	113.951	99.125	151.09	0.74497
11	87.943	199.762	99.125	11.561	0.40125
12	87.943	199.762	44.165	151.09	0.76987
13	44.989	113.951	44.165	11.561	0.76785
14	87.943	199.762	44.165	11.561	0.53773
15	44.989	199.762	44.165	11.561	0.65627
16	44.989	199.762	99.125	151.09	0.75193

The SAW method is applied to calculate the score for sixteen experiments in **Table 7**, the results are also presented in **Table 7**.

From the data in **Table 7**, an equation as shown in formula (5) can be built. The values of all three parameters $R-Sq$, $R-Sq(pred)$, and $R-Sq(adj)$ in this equation are equal to 1, proving that it has very high accuracy [24, 25].

$$S = 1.13063 - 0.00275 \cdot C_1 - 0.0013 \cdot C_2 - 0.00248 \cdot C_3 + 0.00166 \cdot C_4. \quad (5)$$

Equation (5) is used to recalculate the score for the nine options to be ranked in **Table 5**, with the results shown in **Table 8**. The results of ranking options by the DOESAW method have also been summarized in **Table 8**.

Table 8
Score of each option and ranking of options (case 1)

No.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	S_i	Rank
A1	59.844	187.437	44.165	11.561	0.632053	8
A2	87.943	199.762	99.125	49.062	0.464709	9
A3	78.913	127.456	69.874	109.108	0.755758	2
A4	54.816	172.714	60.19	28.588	0.653543	7
A5	63.117	180.361	68.869	99.039	0.716199	6
A6	68.79	113.951	70.694	61.669	0.720371	4
A7	46.654	116.88	92.222	57.177	0.716591	5
A8	44.989	162.337	63.25	55.462	0.731079	3
A9	54.846	167.837	74.165	151.09	0.828496	1

The results of ranking options according to various methods are presented in **Table 9**.

Table 9
Ranking options of case 1 by various methods

No.	Rank [23]							DOESAW
	SAW	WASPAS	TOPSIS	VIKOR	MOORA	COPRAS	PIV	
A1	7	8	8	8	9	9	8	8
A2	9	9	9	9	8	7	9	9
A3	2	2	2	5	2	2	2	2
A4	8	7	7	6	7	8	7	7
A5	6	6	3	7	3	4	3	6
A6	5	5	4	3	4	3	5	4
A7	3	3	5	4	5	5	6	5
A8	4	4	6	2	6	6	4	3
A9	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

The data in **Table 9** shows that: the results of ranking options when applying the DOESAW method obtain a high similarity compared to that when using applying methods. In particular, option with rank 2 (*A3*) when identified by the DOESAW method is the same as when using six of the rest seven methods; option with rank 8 (*A1*) when identified by the DOESAW method is the same as when using four of the rest seven methods; The worst option (*A2*) when determined by the DOESAW method is similar when using five of the rest seven methods. Specifically, all used methods have identified *A9* as the best option. Thus, *A9* is definitely the best option. In other words, the multi-criteria decision-making task in this case was successful when applying the DOESAW method.

The sensitivity analysis was conducted when ranking options by the DOESAW method in different scenarios. Three different scenarios were created using three different weighting methods. In addition to the set of weights identified by the Entropy method used above, two other weighting methods are chosen to be used: the equal weight and the Method based on the Removal Effects of Criteria (*MEREC*) weight. Equal weight is the simplest method, where the weights of criteria are all equal, while the *MEREC* weight is a relatively novel and recommended method [26]. Values of the weights of criteria when identified by three different methods are shown in **Table 10**.

Table 10
Weights of criteria when identified by various methods (case 1)

Weight method	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4
Entropy weight	0.2427	0.25976	0.24616	0.25138
Equal weight	0.25	0.25	0.25	0.25
<i>MEREC</i> weight	0.1366	0.0882	0.1373	0.6379

With the same implementation as above, the use of two sets of Equal weight and *MEREC* weight has built two corresponding equations such as (6) and (7):

$$S = 1.13189 - 0.00284 \cdot C_1 - 0.00125 \cdot C_2 - 0.00252 \cdot C_3 + 0.00165 \cdot C_4, \quad (6)$$

$$S = 0.54345 - 0.00155 \cdot C_1 - 4.41639 \cdot 10^{-4} \cdot C_2 - 0.00138 \cdot C_3 + 0.00422 \cdot C_4. \quad (7)$$

The two equations (6), (7) are again applied to calculate the score for nine turning options, with the results as shown in **Table 11**. The results of ranking options when using such two sets of weights have also been presented in **Table 11**. To facilitate the comparison process, the score and ranking of the options when applying the Entropy weight (as calculated above) are also summarized in this table.

Table 11

Ranking options by the DOESAW method corresponding to different scenarios (case 1)

No.	Entropy weight		Equal weight		MEREK weight	
	S_i	Rank	S_i	Rank	S_i	Rank
A1	0.632053	8	0.635417	8	0.355752	9
A2	0.464709	9	0.463587	9	0.389165	8
A3	0.755758	2	0.752403	2	0.728855	2
A4	0.653543	7	0.655811	7	0.419787	7
A5	0.716199	6	0.717051	5	0.68887	3
A6	0.720371	4	0.717693	4	0.549186	4
A7	0.716591	5	0.715235	6	0.533538	6
A8	0.731079	3	0.733322	3	0.548787	5
A9	0.828496	1	0.828734	1	0.919567	1

Observing the data in **Table 11**, it can be found that although the changes in ranking of some options occur, it is important that the best option (A9) and the option with rank 2 (A3) are exactly the same in all three scenarios. In short, for three different scenarios, A9 is always identified to be the best option. In other words, the DOESAW method was successful in this case.

3. 2. Multi-criteria decision making in the milling process

Data on nine options of a milling process were borrowed for use in this case (**Table 12**) [27]. Two criteria applied to evaluate each option are surface roughness (C_1), and material removal yield (C_2). Where C_1 is the criterion as small as possible, conversely, C_2 is the criterion as large as possible. The task of multi-criteria decision making is to identify an option out of nine where it is simultaneously guaranteed that C_1 is considered to be the minimum, and C_2 is considered to be the maximum. Five methods including Evaluation based on Distance from Average Solution (*EDAS*), Measurement Alternatives and Ranking according to Compromise Solution (*MARCOS*), *PIV*, *MOORA*, and *TOPSIS* were also used to accomplish this task [27]. When performing this task, the weights of criteria C_1 , C_2 were also identified by the Entropy method, with values equal to 0.6641 and 0.3359, respectively. The results of ranking options when applying the above methods will be used to compare with the ranking results when applying the DOESAW method.

Table 12

Data of case 2 [27]

No.	C_1	C_2
A1	0.571	1120
A2	0.818	2400
A3	0.493	4160
A4	0.426	1680
A5	0.47	3200
A6	0.851	2080
A7	0.437	2240
A8	0.694	1600
A9	0.717	3120

The application of the DOESAW method to rank options is repeated in the following order.

Build a decision-making matrix which is **Table 12**.

Identify the minimum and maximum values of each criterion, with the results shown in **Table 13**.

Build a two-level full experimental matrix consisting of four experiments as shown in **Table 14**.

Table 13

Minimum and maximum values of each criterion (case 2)

No.	Min	Max
C_1	0.426	0.851
C_2	1120	4160

Table 14

Experimental matrix of case 2 and results (case 2)

Exp.	C_1	C_2	S_i
1	0.426	4160	1.000000
2	0.426	1120	0.754535
3	0.851	4160	0.668340
4	0.851	1120	0.422875

The SAW method is applied to calculate the score for four experiments in **Table 14**, the results are also presented in **Table 14**.

From the data in **Table 14**, an equation as shown in formula (8) can be built. The values of all three parameters $R-Sq$, $R-Sq(pred)$, and $R-Sq(adj)$ in this equation are equal to 1, proving that it has very high accuracy [24, 25]:

$$S = 0.99654 - 0.78037 \cdot C_1 + 8.07452 \cdot C_2. \quad (8)$$

(8) is used to recalculate the score for the nine options to be ranked in **Table 12**, with the results shown in **Table 15**.

The results of ranking options according to various methods are presented in **Table 16**.

Table 15

Score of each option and ranking of options (case 2)

No.	C_1	C_2	S_i	Rank
A1	0.571	1120	0.641383	6
A2	0.818	2400	0.551986	8
A3	0.493	4160	0.947718	1
A4	0.426	1680	0.799754	4
A5	0.47	3200	0.888151	2
A6	0.851	2080	0.500395	9
A7	0.437	2240	0.836388	3
A8	0.694	1600	0.584156	7
A9	0.717	3120	0.688940	5

Table 16

Ranking options of case 2 by various methods

No.	Rank [27]					DOESAW
	EDAS	MARCOS	PIV	MOORA	TOPSIS	
A1	9	6	6	6	6	6
A2	6	7	8	8	8	8
A3	1	1	1	1	1	1
A4	4	4	4	4	4	4
A5	2	2	2	2	2	2
A6	8	9	9	9	9	9
A7	3	3	3	3	3	3
A8	7	8	7	7	7	7
A9	5	5	5	5	5	5

According to the data in **Table 16**, it can be found that the options ranked 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 are completely identical when applying the DOESAW method and five other methods. The options ranked 6, 7, 8, and 9 when applying the DOESAW method also have a large degree of similarity compared to that when using other methods. It proves that multi-criteria decision making by the DOESAW method was successful in this case.

The sensitivity analysis when applying the DOESAW method was again performed in this case with three different scenarios. Three different scenarios were created using three different weighting methods. Values of the weights of criteria when identified by three different methods are shown in **Table 17**.

Table 17

Weights of criteria when identified by various methods (case 2)

Weight method	C_1	C_2
Entropy weight	0.6641	0.3359
Equal weight	0.5	0.5
MEREC weight	0.3360	0.6640

With the same implementation as above, the use of two sets of Equal weight and MEREC weight has built two corresponding equations such as (9) and (10):

$$S = 0.75029 - 0.58754 \cdot C_1 + 0.00012 \cdot C_2, \quad (9)$$

$$S = 0.50419 - 0.39483 \cdot C_1 + 0.00015 \cdot C_2. \quad (10)$$

The two equations (9) and (10) are again applied to calculate the score for nine milling options, with the results as shown in **Table 18**. The results of ranking options when using such two sets of weights (Equal weight, and MEREC weight) have also been presented in **Table 18**. To facilitate the comparison process, the score and ranking of the options when applying the Entropy weight (as calculated above) are also summarized in **Table 18**.

Table 18

Ranking options by the DOESAW method corresponding to different scenarios (case 2)

No.	Entropy weight		Equal weight		MEREC weight	
	S_i	Rank	S_i	Rank	S_i	Rank
A1	0.641383	6	0.549205	7	0.446749	9
A2	0.551986	8	0.557682	6	0.541226	6
A3	0.947718	1	0.959833	1	0.933546	1
A4	0.799754	4	0.701598	5	0.587999	5
A5	0.888151	2	0.858146	2	0.798627	2
A6	0.500395	9	0.499893	9	0.480197	7
A7	0.836388	3	0.762335	3	0.667656	4
A8	0.584156	7	0.534537	8	0.470185	8
A9	0.688940	5	0.703424	4	0.689104	3

Observing the data in **Table 18**, it can be found that although the changes in ranking of some options occur, it is important that the best option (A3) and the option with rank 2 (A5) are exactly the same in all three scenarios. In short, for three different scenarios, A3 is always identified to be the best option. In other words, the DOESAW method was successful in this case.

Through the two cases just considered above, it can be found that:

- when applying the DOESAW method, the best option is always identified in the same way as when using other MCDM methods;
- the best option identified by the DOESAW method is the same in all three scenarios.

In addition to the above two features, the outstanding advantage of this method is also reflected in the fact that when one/some options is added to the list of options. In this case, if the DOESAW method is used, the ranking of options will be much faster than the current MCMD methods. The following case study will illustrates this statement.

3. 3. Multi-criteria decision making for choosing office microclimate

Office microclimate data were used in this example (Table 19) [28]. Fourteen options are recommended for ranking, each with six criteria including: air volume per capita (C_1), relative air humidity (C_2), air temperature (C_3), illuminance during working hours (C_4), air flow rate (C_5), and dew point (C_6). Of which, C_5 and C_6 are two criteria as small as possible, the remaining four criteria are the ones as large as possible. The COmbinative DIstance-based ASsessment (CODAS) method was also used to rank the options with the weights of criteria C_1 , C_2 , C_3 , C_4 , C_5 , and C_6 equal to 0.21, 0.16, 0.26, 0.17, 0.12, and 0.08, respectively [28].

To demonstrate the advantage of the DOESAW method, let's assume that only thirteen options are initially offered for ranking. That means we will remove one option from the list. An option was randomly choose to remove, for example, option A_{10} , then the decision-making matrix will consist of only thirteen options as shown in Table 20.

Table 19
Data of case 3 [28]

No.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6
A_1	7.6	46	18	390	0.1	11
A_2	5.5	32	21	360	0.05	11
A_3	5.3	32	21	290	0.05	11
A_4	5.7	37	19	270	0.05	9
A_5	4.2	38	19	240	0.1	8
A_6	4.4	38	19	260	0.1	8
A_7	3.9	42	16	270	0.1	5
A_8	7.9	44	20	400	0.05	6
A_9	8.1	44	20	380	0.05	6
A_{10}	4.5	46	18	320	0.1	7
A_{11}	5.7	48	20	320	0.05	11
A_{12}	5.2	48	20	310	0.05	11
A_{13}	7.1	49	19	280	0.1	12
A_{14}	6.9	50	16	250	0.05	10

Table 20
Decision-making matrix after removing A_{10}

No.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6
A_1	7.6	46	18	390	0.1	11
A_2	5.5	32	21	360	0.05	11
A_3	5.3	32	21	290	0.05	11
A_4	5.7	37	19	270	0.05	9
A_5	4.2	38	19	240	0.1	8
A_6	4.4	38	19	260	0.1	8
A_7	3.9	42	16	270	0.1	5
A_8	7.9	44	20	400	0.05	6
A_9	8.1	44	20	380	0.05	6
A_{11}	5.7	48	20	320	0.05	11
A_{12}	5.2	48	20	310	0.05	11
A_{13}	7.1	49	19	280	0.1	12
A_{14}	6.9	50	16	250	0.05	10

The ranking of options by the DOESAW method is repeated in the following order. Identify the minimum and maximum values of each criterion, with the results shown in **Table 21**.

Table 21
Minimum and maximum values of each criterion (case 3)

No.	Min	Max
C_1	3.9	8.1
C_2	32	50
C_3	16	21
C_4	240	400
C_5	0.05	0.1
C_6	5	12

Build a two-level full experimental matrix consisting of sixteen experiments (since the number of criteria is 6, so $2^6 = 64$). Part of the experimental matrix is shown in **Table 22**.

Table 22
Part of the experimental matrix and results (case 3)

Exp.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6	S_i
1	3.9	50	16	240	0.05	5	0.761206
2	8.1	32	16	400	0.1	5	0.820495
3	3.9	50	21	240	0.05	12	0.776444
4	8.1	50	21	240	0.1	12	0.825333
5	8.1	50	21	240	0.1	5	0.872000
...
63	3.9	32	16	400	0.05	5	0.771606
64	3.9	50	21	400	0.1	12	0.784444

Calculate the score for the experiments in **Table 22**, the results are also presented in **Table 22**.

From the data in **Table 22**, an equation as shown in formula (11) can be built. The values of all three parameters $R-Sq$, $R-Sq(pred)$, and $R-Sq(adj)$ in this equation are equal to 1, proving that it has very high accuracy [24, 25]. It is noted that such equation is built on the database of thirteen options (since A_{10} was previously removed):

$$S = 0.29333 + 0.02592 \cdot C_1 + 0.0032 \cdot C_2 + 0.01238 \cdot C_3 + 0.00042 \cdot C_4 - 1.2 \cdot C_5 - 0.00666 \cdot C_6. \quad (11)$$

After equation (11) is built, option A_{10} is again included in the list of options to carry out the ranking process. Equation (11) is used to recalculate the scores for the fourteen options to be ranked, with the results shown in **Table 23**.

The results of ranking options according to various methods are presented in **Table 24**.

According to the data in **Table 24**, it is shown that although the results of ranking options when using the two methods, DOESAW and CODAD, are different, the best ranked option (A_8) and the second ranked option (A_9) both coincide when these two methods are used. It proves that the use of equation (11) to calculate the scores for options and choose the best solution has ensured the high accuracy.

The biggest difference between the DOESAW method and other MCDM methods is that, if the DOESAW method is used, just applying formula (11) to calculate the scores for all fourteen options to be able to rank options. Meanwhile, if other MCDM methods are used, the calculation must be done from scratch when A_{10} is added to the list. Obviously, this is a prominent advantage of DOESAW over other methods.

Table 23

Score of each option and ranking of options (case 3)

No.	C_1	C_2	C_3	C_4	C_5	C_6	S_i	Rank
A1	7.6	46	18	390	0.1	11	0.830902	4
A2	5.5	32	21	360	0.05	11	0.816210	6
A3	5.3	32	21	290	0.05	11	0.781626	10
A4	5.7	37	19	270	0.05	9	0.788154	8
A5	4.2	38	19	240	0.1	8	0.686534	14
A6	4.4	38	19	260	0.1	8	0.700118	12
A7	3.9	42	16	270	0.1	5	0.686998	13
A8	7.9	44	20	400	0.05	6	0.954538	1
A9	8.1	44	20	380	0.05	6	0.951322	2
A10	4.5	46	18	320	0.1	7	0.747790	11
A11	5.7	48	20	320	0.05	11	0.843414	3
A12	5.2	48	20	310	0.05	11	0.826254	5
A13	7.1	49	19	280	0.1	12	0.787062	9
A14	6.9	50	16	250	0.05	10	0.808658	7

Table 24

Ranking options of case 3 by various methods

No.	CODAS [28]	DOESAW
A1	3	4
A2	6	6
A3	9	10
A4	10	8
A5	13	14
A6	14	12
A7	12	13
A8	1	1
A9	2	2
A10	11	11
A11	4	3
A12	7	5
A13	8	9
A14	5	7

Thus, after the three examples above are conducted, it can be shown that:

- the use of the DOESAW method not only identifies the best options like other MCDM methods, but the best option also remains unchanged when implemented in different scenarios;
- for the DOESAW method: even after the regression equation has been built, if one/several options are added to the list, only the regression equation is required to calculate the scores for the options and rank such options, instead of having to perform the calculation from scratch like the current MCDM methods. This is considered to be the biggest contribution discovered by this study.

3. 4. Limitations and development of this research

The biggest limitation of this study is that when an alternative is added, the minimum/maximum value of criterion j of that alternative is less/greater than all the minimum/maximum values of criterion j of the previous alternatives. Then, using the regression equation to calculate the scores for the additional solutions is difficult to ensure accuracy. This limitation should be overcome as soon as possible.

Based on the successes achieved by the DOESAW method in this study, the combination of DOE with other MCDM methods is a reliable direction for further studies.

4. Conclusions

The use of the DOESAW method always identifies the best option, same as when using other MCDM methods.

The best option is identified by the DOESAW method regardless of the weighting method for the criteria.

When a certain option is added to the list of options, the use of the DOESAW method is much faster than the use of other MCDM methods.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest in relation to this paper, as well as the published research results, including the financial aspects of conducting the research, obtaining and using its results, as well as any non-financial personal relationships.

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Data availability

Manuscript has data included as electronic supplementary material.

References

- [1] Zopounidis, C., Doumpos, M. (Eds.) (2017). Multiple Criteria Decision Making. Applications in Management and Engineering. Springer, 211. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-39292-9>
- [2] Prasetyo, B., Baroroh, N. (2016). Fuzzy Simple Additive Weighting Method in the Decision Making of Human Resource Recruitment. Lontar Komputer : Jurnal Ilmiah Teknologi Informasi, 7 (3), 174. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24843/lkjiti.2016.v07.i03.p05>
- [3] Vafaei, N., Ribeiro, R. A., Camarinha-Matos, L. M. (2022). Assessing Normalization Techniques for Simple Additive Weighting Method. Procedia Computer Science, 199, 1229–1236. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.procs.2022.01.156>
- [4] Goodridge, W. S. (2016). Sensitivity Analysis Using Simple Additive Weighting Method. International Journal of Intelligent Systems and Applications, 8 (5), 27–33. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5815/ijisa.2016.05.04>
- [5] Pangaribuan, I., Beniyanto, A. (2020). Multi-criteria decision-making method for procurement of goods and services auction system. Journal of Engineering Science and Technology, Special Issue on INCITEST2020, 26–32. Available at: https://jestec.taylors.edu.my/Special%20Issue%20INCITEST2020/INCITEST2020_04.pdf
- [6] Mitra, S., Goswami, S. S. (2019). Application of Simple Average Weighting Optimization Method in the Selection of Best Desktop Computer Model. Advanced Journal of Graduate Research, 6 (1), 60–68. doi: <https://doi.org/10.21467/ajgr.6.1.60-68>
- [7] Salehi, A., Izadikhah, M. (2014). A novel method to extend SAW for decision-making problems with interval data. Decision Science Letters, 3 (2), 225–236. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.dsl.2013.11.001>
- [8] Afshari, A., Mojahed, M., Yusuff, R. M. (2010). Simple Additive Weighting approach to Personnel Selection problem. International Journal of Innovation, Management and Technology, 1 (5), 511–515. Available at: <http://ijimt.org/papers/89-M474.pdf>
- [9] Abdullah, L., Zamri, N., Goh, C. M. (2019). Application of Interval Type 2 Fuzzy SAW in Flood Control Project. International Journal of Advances in Soft Computing and its Applications, 11 (3), 124–137. Available at: http://www.i-csrs.org/Volumes/ijasca/8_p124-137_Application%20of%20Interval%20Type%20%20Fuzzy%20SAW%20in%20Flood%20Control%20Project.pdf
- [10] Vujicic, M., Papic, M., Blagojevic, M. (2017). Comparative analysis of objective techniques for criteria weighing in two MCDM methods on example of an air conditioner selection. Tehnika, 72 (3), 422–429. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5937/tehnika1703422v>
- [11] Ajay, D., Manivel, M., Aldring, J. (2019). Neutrosophic Fuzzy SAW Method and It's Application. The International journal of analytical and experimental modal analysis, 11 (8), 881–887. Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/343761247_Neutrosophic_Fuzzy_SAW_Method_and_It's_Application
- [12] Zein Eldin, R. A., Abdullah, B. M. (2017). Comparing Two Multi-Criteria Approaches to Investigate Their Ability in Measuring Efficiency. International Journal for Modern Trends in Science and Technology, 03 (02), 52–56. Available at: <http://ijmtst.com/vol3issue2/256IJMTST030237.pdf>
- [13] Gokgoz, F., Yalcin, E. (2019). An Integrated Approach to the World Cup Teams using Entropy based ARAS and SAW Methods. ILLHSS-19, ICIT-19, IABMS-19. Istanbul. doi: <https://doi.org/10.17758/uruae8.uh12194007>

- [14] Panjaitan, M. I. (2019). Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) method in Determining Beneficiaries of Foundation Benefits. *Jurnal Teknologi Komputer*, 13 (1), 19–25. Available at: <https://media.neliti.com/media/publications/326766-simple-additive-weighting-saw-method-in-f8f093e8.pdf>
- [15] Larasati, P. D., Irawan, A. (2020). Application for Lecturer Recruitment Using Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) Method Case Study: Tanri Abeng University Jakarta. *Applied Information System and Management (AISM)*, 3 (1), 15–20. doi: <https://doi.org/10.15408/aism.v3i1.9184>
- [16] Loa, A., Daniawan, B., Tugiman, T., Basri, A. (2020). Comparing SAW and CPI Method in Decisions Systems Support to Evaluate Teachers Performance. *bit-Tech*, 2 (3), 121–130. Available at: <https://jurnal.kdi.or.id/index.php/bt/article/view/141>
- [17] Cahyapratama, A., Sarno, R. (2018). Application of Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP) and Simple Additive Weighting (SAW) methods in singer selection process. 2018 International Conference on Information and Communications Technology (ICOIACT). doi: <https://doi.org/10.1109/icoiaact.2018.8350707>
- [18] Dobrovolskienė, N., Pozniak, A. (2021). Simple Additive Weighting versus Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to an Ideal Solution: which method is better suited for assessing the sustainability of a real estate project. *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues*, 8 (4), 180–196. doi: [https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2021.8.4\(10\)](https://doi.org/10.9770/jesi.2021.8.4(10))
- [19] Biswas, T. K., Chaki, S. (2022). Applications of Modified Simple Additive Weighting Method in Manufacturing Environment. *International Journal of Engineering*, 35 (04), 830–836. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5829/ije.2022.35.04a.23>
- [20] Kusumadewi, S., Hartati, S., Harjoko, A., Wardoyo, R. (2006). *Fuzzy Multi-Attribute Decision Making (FUZZY MADM)*. Yogyakarta: Penerbit Graha Ilmu.
- [21] Singh, R., Dureja, J. S., Dogra, M., Randhawa, J. S. (2019). Optimization of machining parameters under MQL turning of Ti-6Al-4V alloy with textured tool using multi-attribute decision-making methods. *World Journal of Engineering*, 16 (5), 648–659. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1108/wje-06-2019-0170>
- [22] Dean, A., Voss, D., Draguljić, D. (2007). *Design and Analysis of Experiments*. Springer, 840. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-52250-0>
- [23] Duc Trung, D. (2021). A combination method for multi-criteria decision making problem in turning process. *Manufacturing Review*, 8, 26. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1051/mfreview/2021024>
- [24] Trung, D. D. (2020). Influence of Cutting Parameters on Surface Roughness during Milling AISI 1045 Steel. *Tribology in Industry*, 42 (4), 658–665. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24874/ti.969.09.20.11>
- [25] Trung, D. D. (2021). Influence of Cutting Parameters on Surface Roughness in Grinding of 65G Steel. *Tribology in Industry*, 43 (1), 167–176. doi: <https://doi.org/10.24874/ti.1009.11.20.01>
- [26] Trung, D. D., Thinh, H. X. (2021). A multi-criteria decision-making in turning process using the MAIRCA, EAMR, MARCOS and TOPSIS methods: A comparative study. *Advances in Production Engineering & Management*, 16 (4), 443–456. doi: <https://doi.org/10.14743/apem2021.4.412>
- [27] Trung, D. D. (2021). Application of EDAS, MARCOS, TOPSIS, MOORA and PIV Methods for Multi-Criteria Decision Making in Milling Process. *Strojnícky Časopis - Journal of Mechanical Engineering*, 71 (2), 69–84. doi: <https://doi.org/10.2478/scjme-2021-0019>
- [28] Ghorabae, M. K., Zavadskas, E. K., Turskis, Z., Antucheviciene, J. (2016). A new combinative distance-based assessment (CODAS) method for multi-criteria decision-making. *Economic Computation and Economic Cybernetics Studies and Research*, 50 (3), 25–44. Available at: <https://ideas.repec.org/a/cys/ecocyb/v50y2016i3p25-44.html>

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